

Analysis of the influence of job satisfaction and work motivation on employee performance at PT PLN (PERSERO)

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Abstract:

Employee performance is the work achieved by a person or group of people in accordance with the authority or responsibility of each employee during a specific period. Many factors affect employee performance, including job satisfaction and motivation. Job satisfaction reflects one's feelings toward his work. Motivation is a management action to encourage employees to improve their careers through performance. Performance assessments aim to assess employee performance. This research is quantitative research with correlational approach which aims to analyze and test the causal relationship between aims to know the influence of motivation, compensation and competence to employee performance. The population in this research is all employees in PT. PLN (Persero) Power Plant North Sumatera subsidiary, totaling 142 employees. Sample determination using Slovin formula resulted in 59 research samples. Data collection method uses questionnaire, documentation study and interview while data analysis uses multiple linier regression consisting of F test simultaneously and partial t test. The results showed that job satisfaction and motivation simultaneously had a significant effect on employee performance. Partially, motivation has a significant effect on employee performance. The influence of job satisfaction and motivation on employee performance is 63.1%. To PT PLN (Persero) Power Plant North Sumatera, subsidiary, it is advisable to pay attention to aspect that can improve employee performance such as job satisfaction and work motivation to employee performance can be improved. To PT. PLN (Persero) Power Plant North Sumatera subsidiary is advised to further improve its performance according to motivation, provided without waiting for a recommendation from the leader so that personal performance can be further enhanced.

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INTRODUCTION

Employees are highly valued corporate assets and they must be well managed to make optimal contributions especially in terms of performance. Modern companies today have to turn employees into assets, it's not just a production tool. High employee performance is strongly influenced by job satisfaction and motivation. Job satisfaction is a pleasant emotional state by how workers view their work. Job satisfaction reflects one's feelings toward his work that can be seen from employee attitudes toward work and everything in his working environment. Job satisfaction is individual and more aspects of work that are in line with the desire and value system adopted by individuals will be higher in the level of job satisfaction. Employees who have good job satisfaction can be seen from their work attitude not only doing the job but also engage in interaction with their colleagues, supervisors, following certain rules and work environment that are often inadequate or less profitable. Employees with good job satisfaction usually have a record of attendance, work turnover and good performance compared to employees who have no job satisfaction. In addition to job satisfaction, the company must also pay attention to employee motivation in working to always have high motivation and focus on corporate goals. Maintaining employee motivation is more important because motivation is the driving force for each one to act and do something. Without good working motivation, employees will not want to do something that is optimal from within itself. Manpower is the most important resource to consider because these elements in practice can improve other production factors. One of the key elements of the workforce to consider is performance. Performance is a measure of how well employees work in their work compared to the standards. Performance has considerable benefits for employees and organizations or companies as a whole. Improved performance creates opportunities for employees to earn higher wages or rewards and other awards, which means it will improve the welfare level. Increasing the performance of each employees which will also increase the performance of the company as a whole. As such, companies should strive to ensure that employees can always work with high performance, by managing factors that affect performance. Similarly with PT. PLN (Persero) Power Plant North Sumatera subsidiary, to optimize employee performance, supervise subordinate assessment. Evaluation of performance by leaders should be objective and not involve emotions (halo effects) which is a personal assessment of their employees. PT. PLN (Persero) Power Plant subsidiary North Sumatera is a state-owned enterprise serving people throughout the archipelago, committed to providing the best electrical services and meeting internationally recognized electrical standards. The key indicators of employee performance are the quality of work and completion of work standards. According to an interview with staff members of the Department of Human Resources, that PT. PLN (Persero) Power Plant North Sumatera subsidiary needs highly loyalty employees to maintain the stability and continuity of the company. Employee performance is one of the indicators of a company's success. Performance illustrates the actual behavior of employees in the form of work achievements produced in accordance with their respective roles within the company. Employee performance is the level at which the employee achieves job requirements Employee performance is influenced by employee satisfaction and motivation. Job satisfaction is the form of a person's feelings toward his work, work situation and his relationship with colleagues. Thus, job satisfaction is important for an employee, where they can interact with their work environment until the work can be implemented properly and according to the company's goals. Job satisfaction is a fun or unpleasant emotional state of how employees perceive their work. Job satisfaction reflects one's feelings toward his work (Handoko 2010). Ibrar et al. (2015) states that job satisfaction is closely related to many phenomena within the

organization, such as: motivation, performance, leadership, attitude, conflict, and morals. Schermerhorn in Parvin and Kabir (2011) describes job satisfaction as an effective and emotional response to various aspects of employee work. Job satisfaction is aimed at satisfying the needs of employees in working. Employee performance is influenced by job satisfaction and work motivation. Robin and Judge (2010) define motivation as a process that describes the intensity, direction and diligence of an individual to achieve his or her goals. The influence of motivation on performance can be seen from the support activities that lead to the goal (Sulistiyani and Rosidah, 2012). Motivation from inside employees may come from the need for money, rewards, power, and recognition. External motivation may come from family, coworkers or managers. On the basis of the motivation given can be divided into two (Robbins, 2011), ie positive motivation and negative motivation. Positive motivation is the process of influencing people by giving the possibility of reward while negative motivation is the process of influencing someone through fears like loss of recognition, money or position. From the previous description, this research is to analyze the factors that influence the decrease of employee performance, especially related to job satisfaction and employee motivation at PT. PLN (Persero) Power Plant, North Sumatra subsidiary.

The problem in this research is the decrease of employee performance achievement by 3% in 2015, 6% in 2016 and 8% in 2017. Therefore the problem statement in this research is:

1. How the influence of job satisfaction and work motivation on the decline in employee performance in PT. PLN (Persero) Power Plant, North Sumatra subsidiary?
2. What strategies can be implemented to address the decline in employee performance of PT. PLN (Persero) Power Plant, North Sumatra subsidiary?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Understanding Performance

For everyone who is in the management of human resources generally agree that employee performance is an important part of the entire employee process. The importance of rational and objective work achievement covers at least two interests namely the interests of the employees concerned and the interests of the organization. Etymologically, performance comes from word performance. According to Sedarmayanti (2012), performance is defined as work achievement and work performance, and work results. Operational performance can be defined as an action or execution of tasks that have been completed by a person within a certain period of time and can be measured. Performance is the result of quality and quantity work achieved by an employee in performing his duties in accordance with the responsibilities assigned to him (Mangkunegara, 2012). Prawirosentono (2012) states that performance is something that a person or group within the organization achieves in accordance with their respective authorities and responsibilities in order to achieve legal, non-violent, moral and ethical goals. Employee performance is the work achieved by a person or group of people in accordance with the authority or responsibility of each employee during a specific period. According to Mathis and Jackson (2012), performance is how well employees work on their job compared to a set of standards and then communicating the information. Furthermore, according to Adoir (2010), work achievement is the feeling that leads a person to success, completion of work, problem solving and success. According to Mangkunegara (2012), there are several performance indicators as follows (1) Quality of work (2) Quantity of work (3) Execution of tasks (4) Responsibility for work. While according to Sari in Gomes (2012) that employee performance can be measured through the following indicators 1) Quality of work; 2) Quantity of work; 3) Timing accuracy; 4) Level of attendance at work; 5) Cooperation.

Understanding Performance Evaluation

According to Munandar (2010), performance appraisal (performance rating) is a process of assessing personality traits, work behaviors, and work results of employees (workers and managers), which are considered to support their performance, which are used as consideration for recruitment decisions about actions on the field of employment. A company performs a performance assessment based on the consideration that an objective evaluation system is necessary for the organization. In addition, with performance appraisal, top managers may consider an objective basis to compensate in accordance with the achievements contributed by each center of accountability to the company as a whole. Performance assessment is one of the key elements to developing an organization effectively and efficiently because of the existence of a work performance appraisal policy or program means that the organization has made good use of existing human resources. For each company, it is necessary to have relevant and reliable information about the achievement of each individual. Information is also good quality and valid. Hasbullah (2011) asserted that performance appraisal (performance appraisal) is an organization's process of evaluating individual work. In the performance appraisal of the employee's contribution to the organization during the auxiliary time period. Performance feedback lets employees know how well they work compared to organizational standards. Hasibuan (2012) defines performance appraisal as manager activity to evaluate employee work and set forth further wisdom. Furthermore, it is also stated that performance appraisal is to assess the real workflow ratio by the quality and quantity standards produced by each employee. There are several reasons why it is important to assess employee performance as follows (1) performance appraisal provides information as a basis for decision-making on promotions and salaries; (2) performance assessment provides an opportunity to jointly review effective behavior with good work between managers and employees or vice versa; (3) performance assessment allows between managers and employees to develop a plan to correct any definitions that may be known. According to Mathis and Jackson (2012), work performance assessments consist of "identifying, encouraging, measuring, evaluating, improving and rewarding employees performance. While Wursanto (2009) stated that the performance assessment is a list containing the results of the assessment of the implementation of the work of an employee within a one-year period made by the competent authority. In detail Prawirosentono (2012) explains that factors affecting performance include the individual, psychological and organizational factors.

Understanding Job Satisfaction

Widodo (2015) suggests that job satisfaction is a pleasant condition or a more subjective employee's feelings, and it is more dependent on the individual and their work environment, and job satisfaction is a multidisciplinary concept that can be used as a whole or refers to a person's job. Rivai and Ramly (2013) argue that job satisfaction is essentially an individual. Each individual has a different level of satisfaction in accordance with the value system that applies to them. The higher the assessment of the perceived activity in line with the individual's desire, the greater the satisfaction of the activity. Thus, satisfaction is an evaluation that illustrates a person's feelings of pleasure or displeasure, satisfaction or satisfaction in working. Sutrisno (2010) expresses satisfaction of work is a pleasant or unpleasant emotional state for employees in looking at their work. Job satisfaction reflects one's feelings toward his work and appears in a positive attitude toward work and everything that his environment is facing.

Darmawan (2013) argues that job satisfaction is a cognition and affective response from an employee to any work or other work-related conditions such as pay, work environment, co-workers and managers. Priansa (2014) argues that high job satisfaction will encourage the realization of organizational goals effectively. Meanwhile, a low level of job satisfaction is a threat that will bring destruction or setbacks to the organization quickly or slowly. Job Satisfaction theory to find out what needs to satisfy and encourage one's spirit of individual work, namely: a) Equity theory which is that people will feel satisfied and dissatisfied, depending on whether he feels the existence of equity. b) Two factor theory suggests that job satisfaction and job dissatisfaction are part of different variable groups. There are several factors that determine job satisfaction in the company (Widodo, 2015), among others the work itself; supervision; workers); promotion and salary.

Understanding Work Motivation

Work motivation is the urge, effort and desire that exists in human being that activates, empowers and directs the behavior in the execution of tasks in the work environment. The essence of working motivation is the urge to do everything better than others in doing activities to achieve the goal. Motivation is a desire within a person who causes action. According to Siagian (2011), motivation is the driving force that causes a member of the organization willing and to mobilize their ability (in the form of expertise or skills) and the time to carry out various activities that are responsible and fulfill their obligations, to achieve organization goals pre-determined. In Herzberg's theory (Waheed, 2011) he explains that motivation is divided into two factors that are often referred to as intrinsic motivation and hygiene factors or often referred to as extrinsic motivations that are separated into two dimensions. Intrinsic motivation is a motivation that encourages individuals to have the achievement that is sourced within the individual who is better known by motivational factors. There are two types of motivation. Positive motivation is a positive impulse. Managers motivate employees by giving rewards to those who perform well. With this good motivation the employee's morale will be high because humans are generally happy to accept the fine. Negative motivation is to encourage employees with penalties. Managers motivate employees by giving punishment to those who are performing poorly. Theoretically, there are four motivational patterns, achievement motivation; affiliation motivation; competence motivation and power motivation. Factors that create motivation include achievement; advancement; work itself; recognition; security; company reputation; co-workers; salaries; working conditions and benefits. There are several hypotheses proposed in this study as follows:

- H1: Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance
- H2: Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance
- H3: Job satisfaction and work motivation simultaneously have a positive effect on performance

RESEARCH METHODS

The type of research in this paper is a correlational study, which aims to analyze and examine causal relationships among job satisfaction, motivation and performance. The analysis tool in this research is using multiple linier regression analysis which consists of simultaneous test (F-test) and partial test (t-test). The research population is the entire employee at PT. PLN (Persero) totaling 142 employees. In determining the number of research samples used slovin formula. From calculations with slovin formula, the number of research samples was obtained by 59 respondents. Sampling method with stratified proportionality, since research

data comes from five different divisions in PT. PLN (Persero). Collecting research data through questionnaires, documentation and interviews.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Results

Validity Tests

Table 1: Validity Test Results

Variables & Item	r-count value	r-critical value	Description
(X1) Job Satisfaction (JS)			
JS1	.743	0.36	Valid
JS2	.571	0.36	Valid
JS3	.402	0.36	Valid
JS4	.411	0.36	Valid
JS5	.785	0.36	Valid
JS6	.396	0.36	Valid
JS7	.777	0.36	Valid
JS8	.411	0.36	Valid
JS9	.794	0.36	Valid
JS10	.656	0.36	Valid
(X2) Work Motivation			
WM1	.596	0.36	Valid
WM 2	.692	0.36	Valid
WM 3	.468	0.36	Valid
WM 4	.371	0.36	Valid
WM 5	.709	0.36	Valid
WM 6	.513	0.36	Valid
WM 7	.678	0.36	Valid
WM 8	.469	0.36	Valid
(Y) Performance (EP)			
EP1	.499	0.36	Valid
EP2	.693	0.36	Valid
EP3	.508	0.36	Valid
EP4	.485	0.36	Valid
EP5	.614	0.36	Valid
EP6	.695	0.36	Valid

Table 1 presents the results of the validity test for each statement. The results of data processing indicate that all statements are valid, because the r-count value is higher or equal to the r-critical value of 0.36.

Reliability Test

The measurement of the variables is done once, and the results are compared to other questions to measure the correlation between the answers to the questions. According to Sekaran (2006), generally, a variable is stated to be reliable if it provides a Cronbach Alpha value is higher than 0.60.

Table 2 : Reliability Test Results

Variables	Alpha Cronbach value	Description
Job Satisfaction (X ₁)	0.870	Reliable
Work Motivation (X ₂)	0.829	Reliable
Performance (Y)	0.816	Reliable

Table 2 presents the alpha Cronbach value for all constructs: 0.870, 0.829 and 0.816, where the r-critical value is 0.36. It is stated that the Cronbach value is higher than r-critical value.

Multiple Linear Regression

Table 3: Multiple Linear Regression

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	
(Constant)	.646	2.422		
Job Satisfaction	.303	.058	.443	.000
Work Motivation	.310	.049	.533	.000

Table 3 presents the results of data processing to determine the following multiple linear regression equation is: $Y = 0.646 + 0.303X_1 + 0.310X_2 + e$

Hypothesis Test

Simultaneous Test Results (F-Test)

Table 4: Simultaneous Test Results

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	260.225	2	130.113	50.631	.000 ^a
Residual	143.910	56	2.570		
Total	404.136	58			

Predictors: (Constant), Job Satisfaction, Work Motivation

Dependent Variable: Performance

From Table 4, the significance level of F-test is 0,000 ($p < 0,05$). It means there is a significant effect of job satisfaction (X₁) and work motivation (X₂) on employees performance (Y) simultaneously.

Partial test (T-Test)

Table 5: Partial Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.646	2.422		.267	.791
Job Satisfaction	.303	.058	.443	5.216	.000
Work Motivation	.310	.049	.533	6.273	.000

Dependent Variable: Performance

Table 5 presents partial test results as follows:

Job satisfaction (X1)

t-count value is 5.216, and the t-table value is 2.0. Evidence shows t-count value > t-table (5.216 > 2.0) and sig value < 0.05 (0.001 < 0.05). It is concluded that job satisfaction partially has a significant effect on the employees performance at 5.216.

Work motivation (X2)

t-count value is 6.273, and t-table value is 2.0. Evidence shows t-count value > t-table (6.273 > 2.0) and sig value < 0.05 (0.000 < 0.05). It is concluded that work motivation partially have a significant effect on the employees performance that is equal to 6.273.

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Table 6: Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.802 ^a	.644	.631	1.60307

Predictors: (Constant), Job Satisfaction, Work Motivation
Dependent Variable: Performance

Table 6 presents the results of Adjusted R Square which is 0.631 or 63.1%. Evidence shows that the research constructs contribute to explain the employees performance which is 63.1% while other factors outside of this research influence the remaining 36.9%.

Discussion

The Effect of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance

The results of the analysis show that job satisfaction has a significant effect on employee performance. This means that the higher the job satisfaction the better the performance of employees. The results of this study are in line with Saranya's research (2014), Influence of Job Satisfaction on Employees Performance - A general Perspective, where the results of the research prove that job satisfaction is highly dependent on the positive mental, physical, and emotional resources of the workplace. In this case partially job satisfaction variable gives a significant positive influence to employee performance. Factors that can be used to improve performance include work satisfaction, because these factors are an important problem for finding solutions to improve performance continuously. Hopefully with more employees with high performance, the overall productivity of the company will increase so that the company will be able to survive in the global competition. Employees are required to be able to complete their duties and responsibilities effectively and efficiently. Employees' success can be measured through consumer satisfaction, reduced number of complaints and achievement of optimal targets. This is in line with Gibson's explanation (2010) that performance is the result of work associated with organizational goals, efficiency and performance of other performance efficiencies. Human resources in this case have a role in the company, so it needs an educated and ready-to-use workforce to support the development of the company. Employees' dissatisfaction can occur if the work is done incompatible with what is obtained from the company. The dissatisfaction of these employees creates undesirable things and can hurt the company concerned. For example; strike action, increased employee turnover, decreased employee performance, and more. That will ultimately reduce the performance of the company itself. Leaders should understand what employees need and know what those wants to make their employees satisfied and improve their performance, hereafter all the consequences, including what and how much bonus they will receive if their goals or goals are achieved. So employees do not do things that are not worth it. Employees with high job

satisfaction certainly have high morale, so their work performance will be maximal. On the contrary employees with low job satisfaction, cause their work performance to be bad. They become uninspired in the work, and this will have an impact on the company. Employee performance has a strong impact on the company's performance. That is why job satisfaction is considered very important, especially to support the company's performance in the competition in this globalization era (Wijaya & Sutanto, 2014). One way to see employee satisfaction and dissatisfaction is by looking at the number of employees coming out and entering a company (Labor Turnover or LTO). The higher the LTO / Labor Turnover number of a company then signals the high level of employee turnover and can certainly reduce the productivity of a company itself. Therefore, employee satisfaction is an important issue to be observed in relation to employee productivity and dissatisfaction often associated with high levels of job demands and complaints. Workers with higher levels of dissatisfaction. Satisfaction is a result that is felt by employees. If the employee is satisfied with his / her job, then he / she will be happy to work on the organization. By understanding the resulting output, we need to know the causes that can affect the satisfaction. This is in line with the opinion that job satisfaction is a fun or unpleasant emotional state by which employees perceive their work. Job satisfaction reflects one's attitude towards his work. It appears in the positive attitude of the employee towards the work and everything faced in his work environment. Personnel or management departments should always monitor job satisfaction, as this may affect the level of attendance, work turnaround, workmanship, complaints and other vital personnel issues (Handoko, 2010). Similarly, Mathis (2012) points out that job satisfaction is a positive emotional state of evaluating one's work experience. Job dissatisfaction arises when this expectation is unfulfilled. Job satisfaction has many dimensions, in general is satisfaction in the work itself, salary, recognition, relationship between supervisor and labor, and opportunity to move forward. Every dimension produces overall satisfaction with the work itself. Abolition of absolute satisfaction level does not exist, because each individual employee differs from its standard of satisfaction. This job satisfaction indicator can be measured by discipline, work morale, and small turnover, so job satisfaction is relatively good but on the contrary if discipline, work morale and labor turnover are big, then job satisfaction at company is less enthusiastic.

The Effect of Motivation on Employee Performance

The result of the analysis shows that the motivation has a significant effect on the dependent variable Y (employee performance). This means that the higher the work motivation is the higher the performance of the employees. The results of this study are in line with Omollo's research (2015), Effect of motivation on employee performance of commercial banks in Kenya: A case study of Kenya Commercial Bank in Migori County, where the results of the research prove that motivation in the form of rewards significantly affect the Employee Performance in the organization. Overall, this research can be concluded that motivation variable has a significant effect on employee performance simultaneously and partially. From here it can be seen that among the two independent variables the most dominant influence on employee performance is the Reward because it has the largest t value and beta coefficient. The results of this study are also in line with Nnaeto, 2018, Impact of Motivation on Employee Performance: A Study of Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education where the results of the research prove that motivation has a significant effect on employee performance. Motivation is the driving force that can create a person's passion for them to do the work with all his efforts to achieve satisfaction. A manager or leader can be said to be successful in encouraging employees if he is able to create the right motivation for his employees. Motivation given

appropriately will make employees more excited in working so productivity and company goals can be achieved (Robbins, 2011). Employee satisfaction is a positive feeling formed by the employee's assessment of its work based on employee perceptions of how well it works, which means that what is earned in the work already meets what is considered important. In this case, satisfaction indicators are (1) satisfaction with pay or wages, (2) job satisfaction, (3) satisfaction with colleagues, (4) satisfaction with promotion, and (5) satisfaction with supervision of work (Luthans, 2011). Similarly, Torang (2013) points out that work motivation means a condition that motivates or becomes a person doing a job or activity, which is consciously occurring. Motivational work is the energy that drives individuals to try to achieve the desired goal of doing their job. Positive motivation is the process of influencing people by giving the possibility of getting rewards while negative motivation is the process of influencing someone through fears like losing recognition, money or position. According to Nawawi (2010), there are two forms of motivation, namely intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation is a work motivation that comes from within the employee in the form of awareness about the meaning of the work being carried out. Extrinsic motivation is a workforce that is sourced from the outside of the worker in the form of a condition that requires doing the work maximally. Similarly, it is also suggested by Rivai (2013) that performance is a function of motivation and ability ". To accomplish a task or work someone should have a degree of willingness and a certain level of ability. The conclusion can be concluded that employee performance is the achievement of work or output or result of work both quantity and quality achieved by employees within a certain period of time in carrying out its work in accordance with the responsibilities given by the company to him. Psychologically, it is a very important aspect of job leadership is the extent to which the leadership is capable of influencing the work motivation of human resources to be able to work productively with full responsibility. This is because of several reasons, among others: (1) Employees should always be encouraged to work together in the organization; (2) Employees should always be encouraged to work and work in accordance with work demands; and (3) Employee motivation is a very important aspect in maintaining and developing human resources within the organization. Luthans (2011) reveals that basically a person works because of a motivation within him, it arises because of the needs that need to be met. Motivation is shown in intrinsic factors and extrinsic factors, in which intrinsic motivation is more oriented towards behavior that exhibits satisfaction in psychological fulfillment such as the desire to earn rewards and recognition from superiors, the desire to be able to live and desire to be in power, whereas extrinsic motivation is more than indirect fulfillment such as materials, work environment conditions, adequate compensation, good supervision, job security, flexible status and responsibilities and regulations (Sutrisno, 2011) Motivation influences employee performance because motivation acts as a driving force that can create a person's passion, where the higher the workforce the higher the performance of the employees. In other words, the higher the motivation the manager gives the employees, the more challenging to maximize performance.

Managerial Implications

The result of this research analysis shows that job satisfaction and motivation have influence to employee performance both partially and simultaneously. Direct motivation have big and significant influence to performance. This suggests that work motivation plays a role as a variable that determines the size or size of employee performance.

Basically the performance of an employee is an individual thing because every employee has a different level of ability in doing his job duties. One's performance depends on the combination of ability, effort and opportunity gained. According to Handoko (2010) performance is the last measure of the success of an employee in performing his work. From that perspective, it can be concluded that performance is the ability of the employee to assume his / her job. Performance is crucial to achieving goals and will encourage one to be better at achieving goals. To measure the performance level of employees usually use the performance system developed through observations performed by the supervisors of each work unit with several alternative assessment methods or by direct interviews with the employees concerned. The information obtained from these performance assessments can be used for supervisors or managers to manage employee performance, knowing what causes weaknesses and successes of employee performance so that they can be used as a basis for determining targets and subsequent improvement steps in achieving corporate business goals.

Job satisfaction is influenced by responses to intrinsic and extrinsic rewards. The intrinsic reward value is the emergence of a feeling within the employee because of the work done. Being included in the extrinsic reward is a feeling of liking for her work, sense of responsibility, challenge and confession. Extrinsic rewards are situations that occur outside the job, for example because they work well in line with what the company expects, then employees get wages, salaries, and bonuses. Therefore, to improve employee performance, company management should always look at aspects of aspects that can bring employees' satisfaction such as wages, salaries, and bonuses that ultimately can improve employee performance both individually and as a whole in the company.

Motivation issues in the company should be taken as a serious concern in Human Resource Management. Today's modern companies make employees an asset, not just as a mere production tool. For that reason the company needs to create a conducive condition that can make the employees feel comfortable and fulfilled their needs, so that their motivation is also to be maintained to achieve the vision and mission of the company. The conducive conditions can vary, depending on the characteristics of each company. But in general, they can be provided with the facilities provided, adequate welfare levels, clear career paths, self-actualization opportunities, comfort and security in working, old-age warnings and others.

One's behavior begins with a certain motivation or motivation. Basically every human being has the motivation to do the job. In order to produce maximum employee performance, the company's leadership and management should increase motivation to employees because the high motivation of each employee is indispensable to increase the company's productivity. High-motivated people will be motivated to work harder and vigorous because they see work not just a source of income but to develop self and devotion to others. Therefore, motivation is important as a person's motivation to produce a work for both yourself and for the company. With motivation encouragement refers to a good impulse from within or outside the body that encourages the individual's desire to perform activities in achieving goals (Daft, 2002). Based on that, it is important for the managerial party to be able to implicate the need for the role of corporate leaders in providing motivation in a planned and sustainable manner so that the spirit and willingness of employees can be further enhanced. For the future, the company is expected to maintain and also motivate employees to do their best.

CONCLUSION & SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

Based on the results of the research and discussion that has been described about the Analysis of the Effect of Job Satisfaction and Motivation on employee performance, concluded as follows: Satisfaction and work motivation simultaneously gives a significant effect on employee performance. Partial job satisfaction has a significant effect on employee performance. Work motivation partially gives a significant influence to employee performance. Alternative strategies that can be applied to improve employee performance are more emphasizing on aspects of job satisfaction than job motivation. This is in line with the t-test results partially where the job satisfaction coefficient (0.303) is less than the work motivation coefficient (0.310).

Suggestions

Based on the conclusions obtained from this study, the author advised the following: To the leadership of PT. PLN (Persero) is expected to pay more attention to the aspects that affect the performance of employees such as job satisfaction and work motivation so that employee performance can be maximized. It is suggested that the leader continuously motivate PT. PLN (Persero), such as rewarding employees for achievement, strengthening family relationships among employees by holding joint gathering and routine meetings every month, recognizing the shortcomings and advantages of any employee characteristics, by applying this approach to optimize employee performance and assisting employees in improve work performance. To further researchers it is advisable to research other factors in this research and to conduct similar research with a broader scale of research to enable a more complete new research result.

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